

Precautions taken by airlines during the pandemic and customer relationship management (CRM): The example of the Covid-19 pandemic

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Article Info	Abstract
RESEARCH ARTICLE	Infectious diseases can easily spread to other regions through travel with the development of air transportation. For example, the coronavirus, which was first seen in Wuhan, China, in 2019, spread rapidly all over the world, and governments took measures to restrict travel. Airline companies suddenly stopped their operations with the "restrictions on air travel" decision included in the World Health Organization recommendations and were greatly affected by this process. During this process, customer relationship management gained more importance compared to normal periods. In this context, the customer relationship management applied in airline companies during the epidemic period in question was examined with the descriptive analysis technique by preferring the qualitative research method. The Covid-19 pandemic was taken as a sample in the study, and the implemented practices were presented. It is thought that this study will be beneficial to businesses in the event of a possible epidemic with the occurrence of different infectious diseases such as MPOX disease, avian influenza A(H9N2) virus, Chandipura vesiculovirus (CHPV) infection, and Oropouche virus (OROV) seen in 2024. In the study, the measures taken by airline companies during the Covid-19 pandemic process experienced by the aviation sector were presented to the reader, and it was concluded that airline companies that managed this process well in 2024 achieved successful results in customer satisfaction.
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1. Introduction

The aviation industry is one of the most globally interconnected sectors, facilitating the movement of people and goods across vast distances. Its operations are, however, highly susceptible to disruptions caused by various factors, including outbreaks of infectious diseases. Throughout history, the aviation sector has faced numerous challenges arising from pandemics and epidemics, which have significantly impacted its operations, financial performance, and overall sustainability. Major outbreaks such as the SARS epidemic in 2003, the H1N1 influenza (Swine Flu) in 2009, the Ebola crisis in 2014, the MERS outbreak in 2015, and most notably, the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020, have collectively demonstrated the vulnerabilities of the aviation industry to health crises. Infectious disease outbreaks, particularly those with high transmission rates, often

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lead to widespread fear, travel restrictions, and a decline in passenger demand, which subsequently affect airline revenues and operational capacity. In many instances, the aviation industry has demonstrated remarkable resilience, with a return to operational normalcy within months following the peak of a crisis. However, the financial toll and the long-term structural changes that result from such disruptions are notable areas of concern for industry stakeholders. To date, many epidemics have occurred in the world, and millions of people, as well as various sectors, have been affected by these epidemics. With the development of air transportation, especially the epidemics experienced in the last twenty years, have had significant effects on the aviation sector. Between 2003 and 2015, during different periods of outbreaks such as SARS, Avian Influenza, Swine Flu, Ebola, and MERS, especially in countries heavily affected by these diseases, there were losses in air transport revenues. However, it was observed that operational activities recovered within a six-month period after the crises (IATA, 2020).

Businesses that could not manage these processes well have experienced customer losses, and as a result, have been dragged into financial losses and even bankruptcy. It has been understood from these experiences that businesses that cannot manage customer relations well can suffer serious losses as a result of decreased profitability in a sector where competition is very important. Strong businesses in the sector can be successful by immediately getting involved in these processes with the decisions they make, innovations, and changes they make, and fast decision-making mechanisms in the light of this awareness and by providing a good customer relations management (CRM). Customer relations management, which requires significant professionalism, is of great importance for airline companies. The COVID-19 pandemic, in particular, has been an unprecedented global event, severely affecting the aviation sector in ways that were not observed in previous outbreaks. It has led to an unprecedented grounding of flights, massive financial losses, and a fundamental shift in how airlines, airports, and governments approach travel and public health safety. This situation has necessitated a reevaluation of the aviation sector's crisis management strategies, operational continuity, and future planning in response to potential future pandemics.

Regarding the subject; Akça (2020) conducted a study on the impact of COVID-19 on the aviation sector, and concluded that there was a significant loss of passengers during this period, emphasizing the importance of crisis management activities. The study also highlighted that the concept of globalization had weakened, and a new era emerged where countries would continue their existence through entrepreneurial and innovative activities within their own borders. Macit and Macit (2020) studied the management of the COVID-19 pandemic in the Turkish civil aviation sector. The study concluded that the COVID-19 pandemic could be the largest crisis faced by global aviation, and that the Turkish civil aviation sector would be negatively affected by this crisis. While flight operations continued, aviation businesses focused on managing the financial aspects of the crisis once flights ceased, ensuring necessary precautions and flight-related planning. Şen and Bütün (2021) investigated the Impact of the COVID-19 Pandemic on the Aviation Sector. Their research found that the gig economy, as one of the important future sectors, could be considered as an alternative for businesses in the aviation sector and for aviation employees, especially in terms of the future of the sector affected by the COVID-19 pandemic. Kalkın (2021) worked on COVID-19 and the future of the aviation sector, aiming to present the crisis within the aviation context and examine it from the perspective of organizational resilience. The study discussed the current situation, the losses experienced, the measures taken to manage the crisis, and provided various recommendations. Hopancı, Akdeniz, and Şahin (2021) explored the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on the aviation sector. Their research revealed that the aviation sector was severely impacted by the pandemic, with airlines losing a total of 1.7 billion passengers and 6.1 million flights. Governments developed solutions such as "Travel Bubbles" and "Immunity Passports" to allow people to continue traveling and provide relief to the aviation sector. Songur (2023) investigated the impact of the COVID-19 Pandemic on the aviation sector: consumers' attitudes toward air travel. The study, which included 424 participants, found a strong correlation between consumers' willingness to fly, flight anxiety, and the perceived threat of COVID-19.

In line with this information in the study, the studies carried out in airline companies during the pandemic period, which is quite important, the measures taken, innovations and changes made will be analyzed. When the literature is examined, it is evaluated that the research will contribute to the field since there are not many studies on this subject. In addition, the study is intended to serve as a reference in the field of CRM for airline companies in the event of a possible epidemic.

2. Theoretical Background

2.1. Concept of Pandemic

In ancient Greek, the word “pan” means “all” and the word “demos” means “people”. The word pandemic, derived from these words, is the name given to epidemic diseases that spread throughout the world, on a continent or much wider, and whose effects are observed all over the world (Parıldar, 2020).

The World Health Organization (WHO) states that a pandemic will occur when the following three elements come together. These elements (Tekin, 2021):

- I. A new disease and not previously known
- II. It can spread in a way that will cause dangerous consequences among people
- III. It can be easily and continuously transmitted from person to person.

The world has witnessed many events and problems such as wars, social revolutions, and political revolutions throughout the ages. These difficulties have brought about many changes and caused structural formations. In addition to these, epidemic diseases have also caused great destruction and difficulties in world history, and humanity has had to constantly struggle (Ceylan, Özkan and Mulazimogullari, 2020). Among the pandemics recorded from history to the present, plague, smallpox, cholera, influenza, dengue fever, tuberculosis, AIDS, SARS-CoV, and West Nile disease are the most important ones. The first recorded pandemic disease is the Justinian Plague, which is known as the first plague epidemic and is thought to have first occurred in Ethiopia between 541 and 750 AD and then spread to Egypt, Palestine, and from there to Anatolia (Sülkü, Coşar, and Tokatlıoğlu, 2021). In the last 20 years, developments in technology and health, vaccine studies, etc. seemed to have made epidemics forgotten. Some epidemic disease types that were effective globally in this process, when records from recent years are examined, are Sars-Cov (2002-2003), Bird Flu-H5N1 (2004-2006), and Mers-Cov (2012) (Ceylan, Özkan and Mulazimogullari, 2020). The most recent epidemic disease is: On December 31, 2019, WHO (World Health Organization) reported some cases of pneumonia, the cause of which is not yet known, through its China office, and it was reported that the cases emerged in Wuhan, Hubei Province, China. On January 5, 2020, it was announced that a new outbreak, which had not been detected in any human before, was a coronavirus. First named 2019-nCoV, this disease was later named Covid-19 and began to be seen all over the world in a very short period of about three months (WHO, 2020).

2.2. The Concept of Airline Companies

Airline companies, by general definition, are defined as “companies that carry passengers, cargo, or passengers and cargo for commercial purposes on certain lines, in return for a fee, and passenger and cargo transportation that is not within the scope of commercial air transportation, and air work and training activities that are carried out regardless of whether they are paid or not, are considered air transportation companies.” We can group them into four groups: airline, air taxi, general aviation, and balloon companies (DGCA, 2022). Airline companies can be defined as businesses that enable activities such as passenger and cargo transportation to be carried out in a very short time, provide time savings, and perform these activities for commercial purposes using aircraft. In another definition, airline companies can also be expressed as commercial businesses that carry cargo and passengers with Turkish-registered passenger aircraft for Türkiye, with a capacity of twenty or more seats.

Airline companies can be summarized as businesses that provide transportation services by air. In addition to this definition, the operations carried out by the airline company within the airport are also perceived as being within the scope of transportation services. Such as baggage, customs, passport procedures, and terminal services. In fact, the service process of the airline company ends with boarding, in-cabin services, and the flight ending at the destination (Gerede, 2002).

Air transportation is among the fastest-growing sectors today (Zhang and Graham, 2020). The most important reason for this is that the arrival time is much faster and more reliable compared to other transportation alternatives and that it has become very comfortable with the services offered in passenger transportation. With technological developments, aircraft have become more equipped, the number of

airports has increased, and transportation convenience and comfort have increased the preference of air transportation by passengers.

2.3. Customer Relationship Management Concept

The concept of Customer Relationship Management can be defined as a strategy that combines processes and technology to keep customer information in a system, ensure customer continuity based on this information, increase business opportunities and provide quality service to customers (Taşpınar, 2005). Customer relationship management can be considered a process. The first stage of the process is to listen to the customer. The other stages continue as learning the expectations of the customers and determining what kind of service is expected or what kind of product is desired. The essence of customer relationship management is the logic of obtaining as much information as possible about the customers. In short, the main element is the customer. All studies are handled in a customer-oriented manner, and businesses start thinking strategically from the customer (Kırım, 2001). Companies that used simple methods to gain new customers until the recent past have now understood that what is valid and important is not to gain the customer only temporarily, but to provide quality service, quality products, accurate, honest services, and products that are aimed at customer needs in order to ensure continuity.

Working customer-oriented has now become a system that institutions have started to implement in order to be different due to today's competitive conditions. To create this differentiation, they need to develop some strategies; being a leader in product, service, brand, or being successful in customer relations are among these strategies. For example, Microsoft and Nokia target customers who want to buy the latest technology and products by applying the product leadership strategy (Demir and Kırdar, 2022).

2.4. Customer Relationship Management in Airline Companies

All sectors in the service sector and service-oriented sectors prioritize the concept of customer satisfaction and customer relationship management. The civil aviation sector is also included in these sectors. The concepts of customer service and customer relationship management are key elements in businesses in the aviation sector, as in every business, and as a result, they determine the sales and profits of the business. Connecting customer bases is an extremely important factor for airline companies. Customer demands and needs should be met in the best way possible, and this should be ensured by ensuring continuity and regularization. Continuous development, providing better services, and ensuring permanence in relationships will allow businesses to reach more customers and attract customers to their own organization (Küçükönal and Korul, 2002). The critical element in increasing profits and ensuring customer loyalty is customer satisfaction, and this element is one of the most important headings of marketing (Khan, 2013). Airline companies, in addition to gaining customers, also attach great importance to increasing customer loyalty. With loyalty program applications, they increase customer loyalty by offering their loyal customers free flights, flight class upgrades, or allowing them to earn mile points as they fly. Airline companies manage all of these with customer relationship management policies (Hadipeykani and Badi, 2017). Traditional and social customer relationship management should be considered much more important for airline companies. Because the aviation sector is a sensitive sector and is very quickly affected by economic, social, and technological changes. In addition, businesses in this sector closely follow not only national but also international competition conditions, national and international regulations, and changes in other sectors (tourism, industry, etc.), and especially implement the regulations immediately. In addition, these businesses are service businesses, and the services offered are very similar to each other. In order for an airline company providing service under these difficult conditions to reveal its own difference, be less affected by crises and changes, and adapt to this situation quickly, it needs to manage its relations with its customers well, create customer value, and gain loyal customers. This will be possible with good, successful, and systematically implemented customer relationship management programs. In order for airline companies to recognize and retain customers, provide customer satisfaction, and develop long-term relationships with customers, they must first change their management and marketing approaches, adopt a customer-focused management style, and determine systems, strategies, and visions accordingly. In 2020, Turkish Airlines implemented the Customer Segmentation and Analytical Modeling Projects, making it possible to predict customer trends and conduct marketing activities in line with these trends. Within the scope of this project, a total of 4 models were implemented: the Customer Abandonment Tendency Model, the Customer Lifetime Value Model, the

Next Destination Model, and the Business Upgrade Model (Turkishairlines. 2023). In order for airline companies to successfully implement customer relationship management, they must first develop their customer-focused strategies, establish the technological infrastructure, combine this technology with business processes, and most importantly, shape the organizational culture in this direction and reflect it on their employees and customers. The basis of customer relationship management is to collect customer requests, needs, demographic information, etc. from many channels. The aim is to define customers by collecting data, differentiate customers in terms of the benefits or value that customers provide to the business according to this data, then interact and communicate with the differentiated customers, and then create customer loyalty by deepening the relationship with them, creating value for them, or providing them with one-on-one service (Zengin and Ulama, 2015).

The two main topics that are important for good customer relations management are customer value and customer needs. It is very important for airline companies to be in communication with their customers and to be able to establish relationships. The vast majority of airline companies apply various methods to increase customer loyalty, ensure its sustainability, and bring customer satisfaction to the highest level; quality service with rich food and beverage content, especially friendly, caring employees, advantages regarding ticket prices, affordable ticket prices, and campaigns are at the top of these methods. The best customer relations management will increase customer loyalty and therefore ticket sales. In this way, the interest of potential customers will be aroused, and sales rates for the future periods will be positively affected (Takala and Uusitalo, 1996). Include the customer in the reward system and reward them is an important element in loyalty management. Airline companies provide this to their customers with the points collection and mile collection systems they offer. Research has revealed that customers are more attracted to points that offer certain advantages rather than a direct monetary value (Wittmer, Bieger and Müller, 2011). By carrying out the Customer Segmentation and Analytical Modeling Projects in 2020, Turkish Airlines created systems that predict customer demands and trends and provide marketing management according to these trends, and developed the four models mentioned.

3. Methodology

The purpose of this study is to examine the measures taken and studies carried out by airline companies in Türkiye to ensure good customer relations management during the Covid-19 pandemic using the descriptive analysis method. Thus, it is aimed to be a reference for airline companies on how to behave in a possible outbreak and on good customer relations management. Another purpose of this study is to record this study as good data for the post-pandemic period and to guide possible future pandemics, and it is thought to be especially important for airline companies.

This study was conducted by scanning the studies conducted on the subjects of “airline transportation”, “customer relations management” and “covid-19” in the DergiPark, TR Index, and TÜBİTAK-ULAKBİM databases, which are considered important in determining and publishing articles studied in the fields of social sciences. For postgraduate theses, the YÖK Thesis Center web page was used, and scans were made from there. The airlines' own web pages and aviation news channels were also used for the research. No date range restriction was made to conduct a longitudinal developmental scan on the subject under investigation. Especially since the Covid-19 pandemic process is very recent, recent data was easily accessed. Keywords (customer relationship management, pandemic, Covid-19, airlines, airline passenger transportation) were used for source selection.

4. Findings of the Research

During the pandemic period in Türkiye, airline companies that were able to provide successful customer relations and financial management, especially Turkish Airlines, were able to manage the process and survive. During the pandemic, the cancellation, refund, and exchange rights of airline companies and the practices and changes made by the company to protect human health played an important role in customer satisfaction. In such periods, considering people's sensitivities and psychological states and especially having

well-trained personnel are very important in terms of customer relations. The first personnel of airline companies who come into contact with passengers are cabin crew. They are the main point of communication in terms of customer relations. Extensive training of cabin crews for communication skills will create very valuable results in terms of both passenger satisfaction and the company (Oktaýsoy, Topçuođlu and Kaygın, 2023). Airlines that informed their personnel during the pandemic period, both through online training and announcements, minimized the problems that would be experienced or were able to solve them without any problems. At the beginning of the pandemic and throughout the process, THY, Pegasus, SunExpress, and other airlines regularly made announcements on their websites to inform their passengers, especially about Covid-19, and directed them to other addresses where they could get more information (Turkishairlines, 2020; flypgs, 2020). In order not to victimize its customers and to ensure customer satisfaction, THY gave 15% of the value of the tickets sold at the beginning of the pandemic period as a ticket voucher to its passengers, so that both passengers could plan their travels for a later time, did not experience any losses, and THY did not lose its liquidity. On March 27, 2020, with the government decision to impose flight restrictions (DGCA, 2020). THY first stopped its international flights, and in order not to victimize its passengers and to maintain reliability, it gave its passengers the right to postpone, open, or refund their ticket dates. International tickets that started before March 20, 2020, and ended December 31, 2020, could be open or changed until this date. As the pace of the pandemic increased, domestic flights were also suspended on April 3, 2020, and this decision was taken to ensure customer satisfaction by granting the same rights to its passengers (Turkishairlines, 2020). With the suspension of flights, THY brought more than 50 thousand citizens who were temporarily abroad to Türkiye with special flights in order to prevent them from being stranded, which is considered another dimension of the success of customer relations management. Another element of preferability was that passengers saw that contact was minimized when they arrived at the airport. THY, Pegasus, SunExpress, and other airlines quickly initiated applications such as contactless baggage delivery, contactless check-in, and orderly boarding of the plane in accordance with social distance regulations, demonstrating their sensitivity in protecting passenger health and reducing the spread of the disease. Boarding passes could be obtained contactlessly on the mobile phone through THY Mobile applications, and the opportunity to go directly to the boarding gate was provided. New arrangements were made for passengers arriving at the counter, and boarding passes were given without contact. Thanks to the improvements made in the kiosks, passengers were able to check in automatically with their Turkish ID numbers and select their seat numbers. The transition to the plane was attempted to be made through the bellows as much as possible, thus eliminating the contact problem on the bus. In order to maintain social distance, the process of boarding the passengers was tried to be done in groups by starting from the back and looking at their row numbers. Airline companies had to adapt very quickly to all the measures and new practices taken with the introduction of restrictions into our lives (Dileep and Kurien, 2022). Airlines that care about the health of the passengers and implement and invest in systems for this purpose have managed a successful process in terms of customer relations. The most important of these systems is the "High Efficiency Particulate Air (HEPA)" filter that prevents the spread of the virus inside the aircraft. The risk of spreading has been significantly reduced with this system. The HEPA system is a system that eliminates almost all viruses and cleans the cabin air by changing the cabin air at 2-3 minute intervals (flypgs, 2020). Airlines that have adapted this system to their aircraft have become the top choice among customers.

In addition to these practices, cabin crew members were provided with online training regarding the Covid-19 outbreak and were required to pay utmost attention to the use of masks, gloves, and face shields during this process. It was important for passengers to pay attention to these practices at every stage of the flight. The "Hygiene Expert Cabin Crew" practice, which was initiated under the leadership of THY, was highly appreciated by all passengers. Seeing that these rules were implemented and enforced was an important element in terms of gaining passenger trust and choosing the same airline company. All airline companies have given great importance to in-flight disinfection processes. Cabin cleaning and hygiene of materials such as blankets and pillowcases were ensured with special chemicals that do not contain chlorine, have appropriate pH values, and do not contain allergenic substances. Hygienic materials such as disinfectant wipes and masks were distributed to passengers in packages free of charge (flypgs, 2020). In addition to standard announcements made in the cabin, new announcements regarding pandemic measures have been added to the systems. In this way, passengers were regularly informed about both mask use and hygiene, and new developments and new measures were shared up-to-date (DGCA, 2020). In-cabin free refreshments

and sales were lifted during the restrictions, and passengers were informed about this through methods such as SMS, airline websites, etc. In a study, it was revealed that food/beverage catering quality service, which was one of the most important factors among the reasons for passengers' airline preferences, fell to the bottom during the pandemic, and health and hygiene measures took the first place instead. Implementing practices to maintain social distance with fewer passengers, using masks and gloves, placing barriers between passengers, regularly cleaning the air, informing passengers, and finally removing in-cabin refreshments were again included in the same study as factors that affected passenger preferences, respectively. As a result, the importance given to health and hygiene issues and taking precautions were the most important factors that people who will travel by air paid attention to (Özkan, 2021). Airline companies acted in this direction and prioritized the health and satisfaction of passengers. Finally, in addition to the services that airline companies have provided to their passengers during the pandemic period, the post-flight customer complaint management process has also been of key importance in terms of managing customer relations. A dissatisfied customer is not actually a lost customer; the fact that the company finds a solution, makes an effort, and offers alternatives for the reported dissatisfaction means that the customer has been regained and is a satisfied customer. It means a loyal customer who wants to receive service again. There is a parallel relationship between customer satisfaction and complaint management. If complaint management is good, customer satisfaction will be good at that rate (Uzun and Özgöz, 2022). The issues that customers who choose airlines for travel complain about the most are generally ground staff behavior, staff shortage, problems in ticket refund and cancellation processes, problems in call centers and online services, and flight staff behavior (İbiş and Batman, 2016). Although there are not enough resources on this subject for the pandemic process, it has been stated that complaints are generally within the same framework during difficult times. Future studies can be conducted on this subject and contribute to the literature.

5. Results and Discussion

The Covid-19 pandemic continues to have an effect on the aviation sector in Türkiye as well as all over the world, albeit at a reduced rate. The travel restrictions taken at the beginning of the pandemic to prevent its spread were a major blow to the aviation sector. During this difficult process, establishing a bond with customers, maintaining service quality, responding to customer needs, and maintaining customer loyalty have become much more important than normal processes. The main source of income for airline companies and the most important element that keeps them alive are the customers they will sell tickets to. During this period when the whole world has shut down, human movement and travel have almost stopped, and airline companies have struggled extraordinarily. Efforts such as making quick decisions, offering innovations, developing measures to facilitate work, providing continuous improvements in customer relationship management, and good management of personnel have achieved significant success. As a result, businesses that have achieved this continue on their paths with little or no damage, having gained new experiences with the experiences they have gained from this crisis.

Airlines have also demonstrated how much they care about their customers by complying with the measures taken by the Ministry of Health during this process. Gaining customer trust is the most important element for the continuation of customer loyalty. These measures can be listed as: mandatory PCR test, mandatory mask use, HES code application, making arrangements for social distance on the plane, imposing a cabin baggage limit, stopping food and beverage activities on the plane, especially cabin crew strictly complying with protective measures (use of masks, gloves, and visors), cleaning the aircraft interior after each flight using special disinfectants, developing cabin ventilation systems, etc. Announcing these measures to customers, both through in-cabin announcements and publication on the companies' pages, has ensured that customers are relaxed and able to travel safely, and has ultimately increased their loyalty to those businesses. When passengers had to travel during the pandemic, they first preferred companies that implemented these measures at a high level. In addition to these, passengers have requested their pre-pandemic preferences during the pandemic. Factors such as flying without delays, ticket prices, safety, etc. have maintained their place among the reasons for preferring airline companies during the pandemic as always. As a result, this study touches upon the importance of customer relationship management in airline companies during the pandemic period and that airline companies that manage the process correctly will be

successful. We can see these results in the reports regarding the number of passengers carried and profitability of the flag carrier airline company and other airline companies in 2023. For example, THY announced a net profit of 233 million dollars in the first quarter of 2023 (Turkishairlines, 2023). The measures, studies, and innovations taken by airline companies that emerged from this pandemic process without any losses in order to manage customer relationships have been of great importance in terms of customer satisfaction, and the results have started to return as more passengers, more loyal passengers, and financial success.

6. Conclusion

The impact of infectious diseases on the aviation industry, particularly in terms of customer relationships, has been profound and multifaceted. The decline in passenger demand, travel restrictions, and health concerns during these periods have prompted airlines to adapt their customer service strategies to mitigate the negative effects of the crisis on customer trust and loyalty. The COVID-19 pandemic has accentuated the importance of customer relations in the aviation industry. Airlines were forced to quickly implement new health and safety measures, enhance communication, and offer flexible booking options in response to the rapidly changing circumstances. The success of these efforts has varied, with some airlines demonstrating stronger resilience by maintaining customer trust through transparency and effective crisis communication. On the other hand, delays in customer support and inconsistent policies from some carriers led to customer dissatisfaction and a loss of loyalty.

In conclusion, the relationship between the aviation sector and its customers is deeply influenced by external crises, and effective crisis management strategies are essential to maintaining customer trust and loyalty. Airlines that prioritize clear communication, flexibility, and innovation in their customer service approaches are more likely to recover from the negative effects of such crises. Moving forward, the lessons learned from the COVID-19 pandemic and other outbreaks will shape the future of customer relationship management in the aviation industry. Airlines must continue to enhance their crisis preparedness, invest in customer-centered technologies, and remain agile in responding to unforeseen challenges to ensure sustained customer satisfaction and loyalty in the face of future pandemics or global disruptions. The concept of CRM has become a more important topic than ever during the pandemic period, and many research articles have been included, especially in the field of social sciences. In this context, conducting qualitative and quantitative research in future studies and analyzing airline companies with different variables related to the pandemic period will make significant contributions to the literature and will create a roadmap in case of future outbreaks.

Ethical approval

Not applicable.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

- Akca, M. (2020). Covid-19'un Havacılık Sektörüne Etkisi. *Avrasya Sosyal ve Ekonomi Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 7(4), 45-64.
- Ceylan, R. F., Ozkan, B., & Mulazimogullari, E. (2020). Historical evidence for economic effects of COVID-19. *The European Journal of health economics*, 21, 817-823.
- Demir, F. O., Kırdar, Y. (2022). Customer Relationship Management: CRM. *Review of Social, Economic & Business Studies*, 293-308.
- DGCA. (2020, Mart 24). documents. Retrieved March 19, 2023, from DGCA: <https://web.shgm.gov.tr/documents/sivilhavacilik/files/Covid-19/covid-19-uoeb.pdf>.
- DGCA. (2022). Educational Institutions. Retrieved November 22, 2022, from DGCA <https://web.shgm.gov.tr/tr/havacilik-isletmeleri/2067-yetkili-havacilik-egitim-kuruluslari>.
- Dileep, M., Kurien, A. (2022). *Air Transport and Tourism*. New York: Routledge.

- Flypgs. (2020). Retrieved March 19, 2023, from flypgs: <https://www.flypgs.com/faydali-bilgiler/ucusun-icin-bilgiler/koronavirus-onlemleri-ve-dezenfeksiyon-proseduru>.
- Gerede, E. (2002). *Globalization in Air Transportation and Airline*. Eskişehir Anadolu University Institute of Social Sciences.
- Hadipeykani, M., & Badi, G. T. (2017). Customer Management in the Aviation Industry: Evidence from Iran. *Journal of Economic & Management Perspectives*, 11(4), 897-905.
- Hopancı, B., Akdeniz, H., & Şahin, Ö. (2021). Covid19 Pandemisinin Havacılık Sektörü Üzerine Etkileri. *Mühendis ve Makina*, 62(704), 446-467. <https://doi.org/10.46399/muhendismakina.874133>.
- IATA (2020). Covid-19 Updated Impact Assessment, IATA Press, 1-9.
- İbiş, S., Batman, O. (2016). *Analysis of Customer Complaints Against Airline Companies*. 3rd International Congress of Tourism and Management Researches (Pp. 317-333). Antalya: Adra Publishing.
- Kalkın, G. (2021). COVID-19 ve Havacılık Sektörünün Geleceği: Havacılık Yönetimi Kapsamında Bir Değerlendirme. *J. Aviat.* 5(1), 53-63.
- Khan, S. (2013). Attaining customer satisfaction! The role of customer value and relation base marketing a study of policy holders of Peshawar Pakistan. *International Journal of Managing Value and Supply Chains (IJMVSC)*, 4(1), 11-24.
- Kırım, A. (2001). *Strategy and One-to-One Marketing CRM*. Istanbul: Sistem Publishing.
- Küçükönel, H., Korul, V. (2002). Human Resources Management in Airline Companies. *Afyon Kocatepe University*, 75-77.
- Macit, A., & Macit, D. (2020). Türk Sivil Havacılık Sektöründe Covid-19 Pandemisinin Yönetimi. *Avrasya Sosyal ve Ekonomi Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 7(4), 100-116.
- Oktaysoy, O., Topçuoğlu, E., Kaygın, E. (2023). Cabin Services and Training as a Profession in Türkiye. *Labor Relations Journal*, 69-77.
- Özkan, T. (2021). COVID-19 sürecinde havacılık sektöründe tüketici davranışları. *İşletme Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 13(1), 687-700. <https://doi.org/10.20491/isarder.2021.1160>
- Parıldar, H. (2020). Infectious Disease Outbreaks in History. *Journal of Tepecik Training and Research Hospital*, 19-26.
- Parıldar, H. (2020). Infectious disease outbreaks in history. *Anatolian Journal of General Medical Research*, 30(Supp: 2), 19-26.
- Songur, A. (2023). COVID-19 pandemisinin havacılık sektörüne etkileri: Tüketicilerin hava yolculuğuna yönelik tutumları üzerine bir araştırma. *Süleyman Demirel Üniversitesi Vizyoner Dergisi*, 14(39), 787-803. <https://doi.org/10.21076/vizyoner.1219103>.
- Sülkü, S. N., Coşar, K., Tokatlıoğlu, Y. (2021). COVID-19 Process: The Türkiye Experience. *Socioeconomics*.
- Şen, G. ve Bütün, E. (2021). Covid-19 salgınının havacılık sektörüne etkisi: Gig ekonomisi alternatifi. *Journal of Aviation Research*, 3(1), 106-127.
- Takala, T., & Uusitalo, O. (1996). An alternative view of relationship marketing: a framework for ethical analysis. *European Journal of marketing*, 30(2), 45-60.
- Taşpınar, H. (2005). *Customer relationship management (CRM) with IT infrastructure*. Ankara: Seçkin Publishing.
- Tekin, A. (2021). Tarihten günümüze epidemiler, pandemiler ve ekonomik sonuçları. *Süleyman Demirel Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi*, (40), 330-355.
- THY (2020). Retrieved Mart 19, 2023, from turkishairlines: <https://www.turkishairlines.com/tr-int/bilgi-edin/iptal-olan-ucusum-icin-ne-gibi-haklarim-var/?faqKey=duyurular>.
- Turkishairlines. (2023, Mart 15). Retrieved Mart 15, 2023, from <https://investor.turkishairlines.com/documents/faaliyet-raporlari/yk-faaliyet-raporu-4q2021-tr-final.pdf>:
- Uzun, M., Özgöz, A. (2022). The Effect of Customer Complaints Management on Customer Satisfaction. *19 May Journal of Social Sciences*, 232-249.
- WHO, (2020, Ocak 5). COVID-19 - China. Retrieved November 26, 2022, from Who.int. <https://www.who.int/emergencies/disease-outbreak-news/item/2020-DON229>.

Wittmer, A., Bieger, T., Müller, R. (2011). *Aviation Systems*. Berlin: Springer-Verlag Berlin Heidelberg.

Zengin, B., Ulama, Ş. (2015). *Customer Relationship Management*, In book: Current Approaches in Tourism Marketing Edition: First Chapter: Publisher: Beta Yayınevi, Editors: Burhan Kuzu - Zafer Öter

Zhang F. and Graham, D.J. (2020). Air transport and economic growth: a review of the impact mechanism and causal relationships. *Transport Rev.*, 40(4), 506-528.

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